

D2.1 Develop standards for assessment of pan-genome completeness

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Executive Summary

This deliverable defines standards for assessing the completeness and quality of plant pan-genomes, with a focus on ensuring reliable detection of gene presence/absence and copy-number variation across multiple genome assemblies. The objective is to provide practical, community-aligned guidance for quality control (QC) of both individual genomes and integrated pan-genome datasets, supporting robust downstream analyses in biodiversity research and crop improvement

The underlying problem is the lack of standardized practices for evaluating pan-genome completeness. Methodological heterogeneity, variable sequencing technologies, and inconsistent gene annotations frequently result in biased gene sets with a lot of missing genes, undermining comparability across pan-genome members and compromising biological interpretation.

Building on extensive expert consultation and a published white paper, this deliverable reviews and consolidates existing sequence-based and annotation-based QC metrics. Rather than prescribing fixed thresholds, it contextualizes recommended practices, referencing evolving community benchmarks such as Earth BioGenome Project assembly guidelines and established annotation tools including BUSCO and OMArk. Alternatives based on repetitive element assessment (e.g. LAI) and gene consolidation or projection approaches are discussed, highlighting their benefits and practical limitations.

Major conclusions are that pan-genome quality cannot be captured by a single metric, that consistency across all members is critical, and that annotation bias toward reference genomes must be actively mitigated. This work establishes a shared foundation for future standardization efforts and contributes to ongoing international initiatives aimed at developing FAIR, high-quality pan-genome resources.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CNV	copy number variation
contig NG50	length at which half of the predicted genome size is contained in contigs longer than this length.
E-PAN	Enhancing Pan-genome analysis in plants
PAV	presence/absence number variation
QC	quality control

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D2.1 Standards for assessment of pan-genome completeness

Background and Motivation

Pan-genomes integrate annotated genome assemblies from multiple subgroups within a species (e.g., lines, cultivars, varieties, accessions, or genotypes) to capture the species' full gene repertoire. Phenotypic variation among lines often arises from the presence/absence (PAV) or copy-number variation (CNV) of specific genes. For downstream analyses and plant breeding, reliable data of such variation critically depends on complete and consistent gene annotations. However, methodological differences, technical artifacts, and the lack of standardized annotation practices frequently result in incomplete or inconsistent gene sets. Hundreds to thousands of genes may be missing in the annotation data of individual lines, compromising accurate PAV/CNV detection and undermining the robustness of pan-genome analyses.

Collection and assessment of suitable methods: published White Paper

As part of our monthly online project meetings, complemented by smaller topic-focused discussions, we systematically collected, reviewed, and evaluated existing approaches for assessing the completeness of individual genome assemblies and their corresponding gene annotations. Many of the relevant methods had already been applied by project members, allowing us to draw on practical experience when weighing their advantages, limitations, computational requirements, and overall user-friendliness. Under the leadership of project partner IPK, the discussion notes and conclusions were organized, refined, and compiled into a white paper, which is now published: Heuermann MC, Barros P, Beier S et al. **White paper: standards for handling and analyzing plant pan-genomes** [version 2; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]. F1000Research 2025, 14:739 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.166538.2>).

Assembly QC of single genomes

Sequence derived quality metrics

To minimize technical assembly biases all assemblies within one comparative pan-genome study should be based on the same and the best at the respective time available sequencing technology in regard to read types, read coverage and assembly procedure. Especially for large and repeat rich plant crop genomes affordable long read sequencing technologies have been such an immense step forward in assembly completeness and contiguity that even previous pioneering pan-genome studies for wheat (Walkowiak *et al.* 2020) and barley (Jayakodi *et al.* 2020) which were still based on short read assemblies are now either in the process or already redone as long read assemblies (Jayakodi *et al.* 2024). After a time of fast paced improvements it seems now that the quality of long read assemblies has reached at least a temporary plateau. Nevertheless since it is still a moving target we decided not to recommend specific sequence derived assembly quality metrics and instead refer to the annually revised living document of the Earth Biogenome Project (<https://www.earthbiogenome.org/report-on-assembly-recommendations>). The current recommendations termed '6.C.Q40' are: >1 Mb contiguity (contig NG50), >90% assigned to chromosomal scaffolds and <1 in 10,000 error rate.

Annotation derived quality metrics

BUSCO (Tegenfeldt *et al.* 2025) and OMARK (Nevers *et al.* 2025) are two well established and widely used programs to evaluate the completeness and quality of gene annotations. Both programs are user friendly with short run times and no extreme hardware requirements. Busco is based on a set of taxonomic specific single copy orthologs covering for Viridiplantae 800 genes up to 10,000 genes for more specific taxonomy subgroups. BUSCO can be run directly on the assembly as well as on the gene annotation, thereby allowing an assessment of genes missed in the annotations. Omark has the advantage to detect contamination from foreign taxonomic clades.

QC metrics based on the more difficult to assemble repetitive space consisting of transposons and tandem repeats would be more telling, but are still less advanced than gene based methods. Currently they still require considerable extra annotation efforts along with a higher computational investment. A more or less established method based on transposons is the LTR assembly index LAI (Ou *et al.* 2018). LAI is calculated at the end of the LTR-retriever pipeline and comes with the advantage of a fully fledged LTR-retrotransposon annotation of intact and partial elements at the cost of a more complex and computational costly pipeline.

Combining single genome QCs to pan genome QCs

The quality of a pan-genome set cannot be adequately summarized by a single QC metric. First, the choice of quality measures depends on the intended application (e.g., evaluating assemblies alone versus assemblies together with annotations). Second, a pan-genome set is only as robust as its weakest member. For meaningful comparability, it is therefore essential that all members exhibit similar QC profiles, without pronounced outliers that could bias downstream analyses.

Datasets for benchmark case studies of pan-genome completeness

We selected the following five pan-genome datasets for our benchmark case studies:

- (1) Arabidopsis thaliana: best-characterized model plant, 8 lines (Jiao *et al.* 2020)
- (2) oilseed rape, a more complex tetraploid genome: 9 lines (Song *et al.* 2020)
- (3) Rice: 33 lines (Qin *et al.* 2021)
- (4) Tomato: 46 lines (Zhou *et al.* 2022)
- (5) Barley: pan-genome version2, 76 lines (Jayakodi *et al.* 2024)

Locating, downloading, organizing and parsing the data from multiple repositories was already a substantial undertaking requiring a considerable manual effort. A centralized repository with an API for machine-readable, automated access would be a major step forward. Currently such a “one-stop shop” remains wishful thinking. This issue is not unique to pan-genomes, but applies generally to new data resources described in publications.

Basic QC metrics for representative datasets

The pipelines are currently implemented and the results will be presented in the final project report.

Gene consolidation approaches

A common yet often overlooked issue in pan-genome annotation is that the reference genome of a species typically contains a more complete and higher-quality gene set than the remaining members. To mitigate this bias, gene consolidation approaches should be applied to transfer annotations across pan-genome members, thereby recovering gene models that may be missing in individual assemblies.

One such approach, developed by the Belgian partner VIB, is described in Deliverable D2.2: Computational pipelines to assess pan-genome data quality and characterize gene-based structural variation within pan-genomes.

Owing to time constraints, an alternative gene projection strategy based on an existing collection of scripts (https://github.com/GeorgHaberer/gene_projection) could not be implemented as a fully generic pipeline. A substantial amount of effort was already needed to preprocess our five case study datasets into the standardized formats required by the pipeline. This preprocessing included, among other steps, harmonizing different GFF file flavors, extracting representative gene models or the identification and appropriate tagging of potentially transposon-related genes. The latter are particularly problematic, as their ubiquitous presence in plant genomes can lead to an unwanted explosion of transferred gene models.

Outcomes and expected impact

As a concrete impact our White Paper caught the attention of the recently formed "International Plant Pangenome Working Group" which brings together a group of 30 international researchers with expertise in genome annotation, plant genomics and pan-genome architecture. The group's aim is to identify strategies and approaches that will accelerate the development of usable, representative pan-genome references and pan-genome graphs. We were contacted by the two coordinators Rachel Pilcher and Anthony Hall (both from the Earlham Institute, UK) and invited them to one of our monthly online meetings. At the E-Pan September meeting they introduced the working group and its mission. E-Pan and the International Plant Pangenome Working Group have some overlapping aims and interests and we will present our results at one of their next monthly meetings.

The E-Pan project is nearing completion, it was only conceived as a short-term initiative with limited resources relative to the scale and complexity of the challenges involved. Nevertheless, E-Pan has succeeded in consolidating and disseminating key ideas and in laying important groundwork. Considerable further effort will be required to introduce, promote, and ultimately establish pan-genome data and analysis standards in alignment with the FAIR data principles.

Dissemination Plans

The outcomes of this deliverable project are presented in a peer-reviewed white-paper published in F1000Research:

Heuermann MC, Barros P, Beier S et al. White paper: standards for handling and analyzing plant pan-genomes* (version 2; peer review: 2 approved with reservations). F1000Research 2025, 14:739 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.166538>).

The results and identified issues from our five pilot study pan-genome datasets will be presented as case studies during the upcoming E-Pan online workshop (Task D 2.6), scheduled for 18 May 2026.

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